

ISic1241

I.Sicily inscription 1241

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140726

1. Θ (εοῖς) □ Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Ῥωσκία Ἑρμι-
3. όνη ἔζησε
4. ἔτη □ λ' □ Ζώσι-
5. μος εἰδία συν-
6. βίω μνήμης
7. χάριν.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492844

EDCS 39101606

PHI 140726

Bibliography

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